

TOWARDS A CIRCULAR ECONOMY: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF CIRCULAR BUSINESS MODELS

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Abstract: *The transition to a circular economy (CE) requires innovative business models that move beyond traditional linear practices. This paper systematically reviews Circular Business Models (CBMs) using the PRISMA methodology, analysing 42 peer-reviewed publications¹. Two complementary classification perspectives are identified: The **Strategic Focus Classification** (design, use, recovery-focused, and hybrid models) and the **Operational Typology** (product, service, resource, and design-innovation CBMs). Together, these frameworks clarify both the rationale for circularity and its practical implementation. Key findings highlight significant challenges, including regulatory gaps, high upfront costs, organizational resistance, and digital infrastructure needs. The review underscores the importance of standardized frameworks and cross-sectoral collaboration to advance CBM adoption and support sustainable economic transitions.*

Keywords: circular business models (CBMs), circular economy (CE), sustainability, systematic literature review PRISMA methodology, business model innovation

1 INTRODUCTION

The CE addresses the ecological and economic limitations of the linear model by promoting reuse, repair, remanufacturing, and recycling (Geissdoerfer et al., 2020). At its core are CBMs, which reshape value creation and capture to support resource circularity (Hofmann, 2019). Yet research on CBMs remains fragmented, with diverse definitions and approaches limiting clarity and adoption. While many earlier reviews have specific focus, this paper offers a broader synthesis that integrates strategic intent and operational architecture across sectors. It addresses this gap through a systematic literature review that traces the evolution of CBM definitions, synthesizes key conceptual categories, and introduces a dual classification, Strategic Focus and Operational Typology, that explains both the rationale for circularity and its implementation. The framework enables cross-sectoral comparison and offers a conceptual foundation for future CBM research and application.

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2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The literature search was conducted between April and May 2025, focusing on peer-reviewed articles published between 2010 and 2025. It was carried out across major scientific databases, including Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, Copernicus, and EBSCO. The search strategy combined keywords such as “Circular Business Models”, “Circular Economy”, “Sustainability” and “Business Model Innovation”. The analysis focused on two objectives: (1) tracing the historical evolution and definitional variations of CBMs; and (2) classifying conceptual models based on strategic focus and operational characteristics. The selection and screening of publications followed the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines to ensure a structured and transparent review process.

2.1 Sample

From 234 records initially identified, 9 were removed as duplicates or irrelevant. In title&abstract and full-text screening, 42 studies were excluded for superficial coverage of CBMs, 32 for addressing isolated sustainability topics, and 37 for being overly context or product-specific. The final sample included 42 publications offering conceptual or theoretical insights on CBMs. Thematic categories were derived inductively, based on their relevance to CBM theory and practice.

Figure 1: PRISMA DIAGRAM

(Limitation: Using specific keywords may have excluded studies addressing CBMs indirectly, though the sample remains sufficient for analyzing their evolution and strategic implications.)

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CBMs have evolved from early eco-innovation efforts into structured approaches supporting reuse, repair, remanufacturing, and recycling, which is essential for transitioning beyond the limitations of linear systems. (Zafar et al., 2021). This review identifies four dominant definitional categories, each aligned with distinct business model configurations. The resulting classification framework reflects recurring patterns across the analysed literature and is grounded in the following dominant definitional approaches:

- **Strategy-Oriented Definitions**-emphasize long-term competitiveness and value retention through closed-loop systems (Puglieri et al., 2022; Konietzko et al., 2020) and next-generation sustainable business models leveraging circular principles (Rosa et al., 2019).
- **Activity-Based Definitions**-emphasize actions like product-as-a-service and reverse logistics (Urbinati et al., 2017), with reverse logistics noted as a strong marketing strategy (Lahti et al., 2018; Guillén et al., 2023).

- **Value-Focused Definitions**-stress the shift from linear to shared or regenerative value (Bocken et al., 2018), with frameworks proposing CBMs that realign value creation to circular principles (Kirchherr et al., 2017).
- **Hybrid (or Holistic) Definitions**-provide integrated perspectives that transcend sector-specific models, supporting wider adoption of CE concepts (Sjödín et al., 2023). For example, a finance-marketing hybrid based on customer lifetime value shows how circular strategies can enhance market equity (Awan & Sroufe, 2022).

The variety of definitions reflects disciplinary differences: while engineering and environmental sciences focus on technical processes, business and management studies emphasize value configuration and strategic orientation. This disciplinary divergence has created challenges in forming a unified definition. However, several researchers (Kirchherr et al., 2023) advocate for hybrid approaches that integrate ecological, economic, and systemic dimensions.

The definitional review shaped the classification framework by revealing recurring patterns that conceptually distinguish strategic from operational CBM typologies.

The implementation of a viable business model is critical to achieving the goals of a CE. Literature on CBMs reveals a wide spectrum of approaches, generally focusing on strategic goals, value creation mechanisms, and business model components. Two complementary classification perspectives are identified: **Strategic Focus Classification** and **Operational Typology** based on business model (BM) architecture.

Strategic Focus Classification is based on the primary logic for achieving circularity, emphasizing distinct approaches to value creation, delivery, and capture:

- Design-Focused CBMs*-rely on eco-design to extend lifecycles, reduce inputs, and enable modularity. Strategies include repair, reuse, remanufacturing, and recycling (Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2019). Key archetypes are design for longevity (Lee & Sicklinger, 2024), disassembly (Den Hollander et al., 2017; Rosa et al., 2019), and reuse (Schulte, 2013; Ferasso, 2020).
- Use-Focused CBMs*-promote access over ownership through Product-Service Systems, leasing, and sharing platforms, reducing idle capacity (Yang et al., 2017; Loon, 2020).
- Recovery-Focused CBMs*-close loops through remanufacturing, recycling, and take-back schemes, enhancing both cost efficiency and consumer participation (Schwanholz et al., 2020; Nußholz, 2018; De Keyser & Mathijs, 2023)
- Hybrid and Emerging CBMs*-integrate design, use, and recovery logics, exemplified by emerging archetypes such as waste-based and platform-based start-ups (Marvin et al., 2019).

Operational Typology is based on BM Architecture and is focusing on business model elements such as value proposition, customer interface, and supply chain design:

- Product-Oriented CBMs*-extend lifecycles through reuse and remanufacturing, common in electronics and machinery (Ertz et al., 2019; Whalen, 2019).
- Service-Oriented CBMs*-emphasize access over ownership, particularly in mobility and fashion, via leasing and sharing models (Heyes et al., 2017; Coscieme et al., 2022).
- Resource-Oriented CBMs*-focus on input substitution and industrial symbiosis in bio-based and agricultural sectors (Donner et al., 2020; Carraresi & Bröring, 2021)
- Design-Innovation CBMs*-embed circularity at the design stage, enabling modularity and repair (Santa-Maria et al., 2022; Scholtysik et al., 2023).

Despite their potential, CBMs face persistent challenges: limited regulatory incentives (Fraccascia et al., 2019), high upfront costs and uncertain returns (Vermunt et al., 2019), organizational resistance to shifting from linear models (Linder & Williander 2015), and infrastructure demands for digital technologies such as IoT and analytics (Sjödín et al., 2023).

Together, the two classifications provide a holistic framework. The strategic perspective clarifies *why* circularity is pursued, while the operational perspective shows *how* it is implemented. This dual lens highlights both overarching logics and practical architectures, while the diversity of classifications underscores the need for greater coherence and standardized frameworks to guide adoption (Frishammar & Parida, 2018). Strategically, CBMs range from incremental innovations that enhance efficiency and recycling, to transformational models that redesign entire value systems through systemic solutions such as closed-loop supply chains and cross-sectoral collaboration (Palmié et al., 2021; Averina et al., 2021). Their application spans firm-level strategies by reducing material dependency and meeting regulatory demands (Moggi & Dameri, 2021;), to broader initiatives like industrial symbiosis and circular ecosystems, reinforcing their role as drivers of sustainable transitions (Angelis, 2022; Geissdoerfer, 2022).

4 CONCLUSIONS

This review confirms that CBMs are central to advancing the circular economy by enabling extended product lifecycles, resource optimization, and material regeneration. Based on a PRISMA-guided synthesis of the literature, this paper introduces a dual typology, *Strategic Focus* and *Operational Architecture*, that clarifies both the intent and implementation of CBMs. This typology offers a conceptual framework for interpreting and applying CBMs across sectors, allowing organizations to align model selection with their specific goals and contexts. In doing so, it enhances the likelihood of reconciling ecological objectives with economic feasibility. Despite their promise, different CBM types face distinct implementation challenges. Strategic models often struggle with systemic inertia, misaligned incentives, and insufficient policy support, while operational models confront infrastructure demands, limited digital capabilities, and scaling difficulties. Understanding these barriers through the lens of typology enables more targeted, type-specific interventions-regulatory, financial, or technological. The proposed framework provides a structured approach for navigating the fragmented CBM literature and supports cross-sectoral comparison and practical application. As interest in circular strategies continues to grow, such integrative typologies will be essential for bridging academic insight with real-world implementation in the transition towards a sustainable CE.

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